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**Heuristic optimization for large-scale energy resource management in
the smart grid context**

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Abstract:

Energy management systems must evolve with the increasing penetration of distributed energy resources today. The significant integration of renewables and other resources, such as electric vehicles, adds to the complexity of the energy resource management problem. These resources add uncertainty and variability to the conventional grid, producing voltage and frequency stability problems. The smart grid can account for this uncertainty and unpredictability by adopting an energy resource management framework. Due to the present problem's complexity, computational intelligence optimization approaches, particularly metaheuristics, are gaining traction when it comes to their use in the energy domain [1]. In contrast to mathematical approaches, metaheuristics allow a more practical problem solving of complex problems while balancing "optimal" and "practical" solutions without requiring the high computational effort that deterministic methods require. So, they are more suitable for large-scale optimization problems. We apply multiple heuristic algorithms to different energy resource management problems in this context. Initially, we apply three different heuristics to a centralized day-ahead optimization problem considering multiple aggregators [2]. We compare the differential evolution algorithm to two novel heuristics. Results show that these two heuristics vastly outperform the differential evolution, mainly when the number of variables increases.

We propose an hour-ahead optimization for multiple aggregators considering five different heuristics [3]. A statical test was performed for the obtained results, which shows that heuristics based on the estimation of distribution algorithms through Normal-Cauchy distribution outperform the other algorithms.

Finally, we enhanced the day-ahead problem by integrating a risk-based framework to analyze the risk associated with extreme events (low probability, high impact) due to the considered uncertainty via conditional value-at-risk [4]. For the 2022 framework competition on the evolutionary computation [5], a hybrid-adaptive differential evolution algorithm achieved the best results when compared to other tested algorithms for both risk-neutral (without considering risk) and risk-averse (evaluating risk) approaches.

Related References:

- [1] J. Soares, T. Pinto, F. Lezama, and H. Morais, "Survey on Complex Optimization and Simulation for the New Power Systems Paradigm," *Complexity*, vol. 2018, pp. 1–32, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/2340628.
- [2] J. Almeida, J. Soares, B. Canizes, F. Lezama, M. A. Ghazvini Fotouhi, and Z. Vale, "Evolutionary Algorithms for Energy Scheduling under uncertainty considering Multiple Aggregators," in *2021 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, Kraków, Poland, Jun. 2021, pp. 225–232. doi: 10.1109/CEC45853.2021.9504942.

- [3] J. Almeida, J. Soares, F. Lezama, B. Canizes, and Z. Vale, “Evolutionary Algorithms applied to the Intraday Energy Resource Scheduling in the Context of Multiple Aggregators,” in *2021 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, Orlando, FL, USA, Dec. 2021, pp. 01–08. doi: 10.1109/SSCI50451.2021.9660005.
- [4] J. Almeida, J. Soares, F. Lezama, and Z. Vale, “Robust Energy Resource Management Incorporating Risk Analysis Using Conditional Value-at-Risk,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 16063–16077, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3147501.
- [5] J. Soares, F. Lezama, J. Almeida, B. Canizes, and Z. Vale, “Guidelines for WCCI(CEC)/GECCO 2022 Competition Evolutionary Computation in the Energy Domain: Risk- based Energy Scheduling,” p. 18.